

Scientific Aspects of Subsistence Behavior & Archaeology of Garhwal Himalaya

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DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16828820>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 26-07-2025

Published: 10-08-2025

Keywords:

Himalaya, Malari, Supana,
Thapli, Alaknanda valley,
Palaeodiet, C₄ & C₃
grasses, $\delta^{13}C$, $\delta^{15}N$

ABSTRACT

Garhwal Himalaya has a rich heritage of myths, legends, and folklore and is therefore, considered as a sacred place of God. The Rock Painting evidence from Garhwal and Kumaun regions possesses its antiquity up to the prehistoric period. The cave of Malari, Chamoli (Garhwal), also gives an indication of megalithic culture in the higher Himalaya. The archeological sites of Alaknanda Valley belong to PGW to early historical period. However, the reconstruction of subsistence patterns through scientific methods in this region has not been done. Because the Garhwal Himalaya region possesses a humid condition, the retrieval of grain evidence has been very rare in the different archaeological sites of the Garhwal. On the basis of these disadvantages, researcher has been carrying out the study of the subsistence behavior of the Garhwal Himalaya through bone chemistry. On the basis of the study, it has been found that the humans of the higher Himalayas consumed C₄ cereals and rich meat contents in their diet. However, on the basis of the analysis of animal bones shows that the C₃ pasture land is still preserved in higher Himalaya (Malari).

Introduction

Garhwal Himalaya is bestowed with a rich heritage of myths, legends, folklore and religion woven inextricably within its cultural folds for ages. This finds inferences in the Puranas and other religious scriptures besides the great epics. In the Balmiki Ramayan and Mahabharata, it has been referred to as

Karupath, Kulinda, or Kunindil Pradesh. In the later texts, Garhwal finds mention of Kedarkhand, Sapadalaksa, Kedarbhumi, Parvatka, etc (Naithani, 1995). Further, there are several references in the ancient text to the religiosity and piousness of the region. The Ganga and other Himalayan rivers have also been greatly extolled in the literary accounts (Mahabharata 158, 15-21). In another reference, Krishna is stated to have propitiated sage Narayana on Mount Gandhamadana and later went for penance at Badrikashrama (Mahabharata 13, 10-13). Again, in the Mahaprasthanikaparva of the Mahabharata, the reference to Svargarohani, Brahma river, Panchprayag and Kedar is significant as all these places have been associated with the existing five important pilgrim centers of Garhwal Himalaya. The later Vedic and Puranic records also provide some stray references to the Khasas and other tribes who had scattered widely in the mountainous region of Kumaun, Garhwal, alongside Himachal (Kullu and Kangra), Kashmir, and up to the Nepal Himalaya (Nautiyal,1969). The Puranas and the Mahabharata also refer to the names of a few tribal groups living in the region, mainly Khasas, Kiratas, Kunindas, and Nagas. There is enough evidence to suggest that the Khasas, along with the Kiratas, were co- existing around the sources of the Ganga and the Yamuna (Nautiyal,1969). The Khasas, during their movement from the North West Himalayan passes towards the east along the high mountain ridges and valleys from Kashmir to Nepal, established their transit hutments on the mountain spurs and entered the Garhwal Himalayan steppes.

The arrival of the Khasas and other tribes in the Garhwal Himalaya had a strong bearing on the history of this region. The Vishnupuran (15-128) refers to Khasas as the daughter of Oaksa, wife of Kasyapa, and mother of Yaksas and Rakasas, while in the Mahabharata, Khasas have been described as living in the Punjab between the Arattas and Vasatis. In successive references in the Mahabharata, Khasas have been referred to as a northern tribe who used to offer presents, particularly pipilika (ant gold), to Yodhisthira (Nautiyal,1969).

1. Archaeology of Garhwal Himalaya

The Garhwal Himalaya has remained darkened in the Stone Age culture, but the rock paintings of the region give indirect evidence of the presence of prehistoric man. The rock art cannot be dated conclusively to the prehistoric period because no datable material or paintings are found at the sites. However, due to its stylistic nature, researchers have dated it to the Upper Paleolithic to Mesolithic period (Agrawal & Joshi, 1978; Nautiyal,1969). The rock shelters have been reported from Dalband in Kumaun Himalaya (Agrawal & Joshi, 1978), Kimni (Nautiyal & Khanduri, 1986), and Dungari (Bhatt & Nautiyal,1988) in Chamoli, Garhwal. The hunting scene is most prominent in the painting, but the human and animal figures are shown very stylistically and actively. The animal figurines depicted in the painting

have been identified as deer, foxes, bears and a multi-legged lizard. This fauna gives evidence of the prehistoric fauna of the central Himalaya. Another subject of the painting was related to naturalism and the way food is gathered.

The rock shelter in Kumaun Himalaya has been reported from Dalband in District Almora (Agrawal & Joshi, 1978). The motifs of the painting have been identified as human and animal figurines, geometrical figures, and other figures. The human figurines are represented as stick and arrow-like forms, but the animals depicted in the painting are identified as foxes and multi-legged lizards. Besides these, a few geometrical designs have been identified, such as wavy lines, black and red arches, filled rectangles, etc. The hunting scene is prepared in red ochre colour. The dating of the painting has not been determined conclusively. However, on the basis of typical stylistic features, authors have dated it from the pre-Neolithic to Chalcolithic. The researchers have reported on a rock shelter with paintings from village Dungri in Chamoli, Garhwal (Bhatt & Nautiyal, 1988). The painting was subjected to hunting scenes, naturalism, and methods of food gathering. Most of the scenes are damaged due to sunlight, winds, and rainwater.

The protohistoric period of the Garhwal Himalaya came to light after the excavations of Thapli (Nautiyal et. al., 1979) and Purola (Nautiyal & Khanduri, 1986) in the Alaknanda and Kamal valleys respectively. The Thapli (30° , 12° N, 78° , 47° E) is located on the right bank of the river Alaknanda, near Srinagar town in Tehri Garhwal. The excavation at Thapli revealed a single phase culture of painted gray ware along with all the associated types of red and black slipped ware. The paintings on these pots are very similar to other P. G. W pottery found from Ganga doab, i.e, leafy designs, dots, sun symbols, etc. Among the pottery another important finding is a red terracotta bird (Nautiyal et. al., 1979).

In the excavation at Thapli, a large number of faunal remains have been found from the excavation. These archeological remains of domesticated animals have been identified as *Bos-indicus* (Indian humped cattle), *Sus scrofa-cristatus* (domestic pig), and *Equus- cabalus* (domesticated horse) are important. Badam has studied these faunal remains and, based on the cut marks, he has been given the opinion that these animals have been used for dietary purposes, and young ones (due to being rich in protein) may be preferred by these settled communities of the Alaknanda valley.

The other site of painted grey ware reported from Garhwal is Purola (Nautiyal & Khanduri, 1986) Purola (31° , 70° N, 78° , 40° E) is situated on the left bank of the river Kamal in Utarkashi district. The authors have reported PGW pottery with associated wares of red slipped, black slipped, grey ware and red ware. Among the faunal remains, the dental and femur remains of domestic horses are an important finding. However, another notable finding of this site is Syenchiti or Garur vedika, datable to the

kuninda period (Nautiyal & Khanduri, 1986). The vedika is made of burnt bricks, measuring 24×18cm in the shape of a flying garuda, which is laid in the east-west direction. The evidence found in the Vedika is mainly Sunga-Kushana pottery, copper coins of Kuninda rulers etc. The bone remains from the pit of vedika are identified as the long bones of sheep and goats. The charred bones of sheep and goats from the pit of Vedika is suggest that these animals have been used for sacrifice purposes.

The megalithic burials of the Garhwal Himalaya have given great interest to archaeologists. Researchers have explored, excavated, and investigated a number of megalithic sites in this region (Henwood, 1856; Wheeler, 1951; Dabral, 1968; Bhatt & Nautiyal, 1988;Nautiyal & Khanduri, 1986). The burial tradition of this region is associated with the Leh valley of Ladakh and Kashmir (Frankey, 1914), Lahul and Chamba in Kangra district (Sankrityanan, 1953) and the Swat valley in Pakistan(Antonini & Staacul, 1972).

The site of Malari (Lat 70⁰ 50^IN, Long. 790 55^I 50^{II}) is situated at an altitude of 3,500 meters MSL in Chamoli district, about 63Km. north–east of Joshimath on the way to Niti pass. A large number of exploration and excavation have not been conducted in this area. However, the earlier work by Dabral(1968) and later on excavations by the department of history and archaeology, HNB Garhwal University under the direction of Prof. K. P. Nautiyal shed light on the cave burial tradition of the Garhwal Himalaya. The excavation yielded the complete horse skeleton and a number of full pots of red and black ware together in buried condition in a cave (Bhatt & Nautiyal, 1988). The AMS date of the horse found at oxford University has been given around 2100±49 BP.(Tom Higham personal communication).

However, an exploration by the department of archaeology (Garhwal University) in 2000 and 2002 found a human skeleton from Malari. The recent findings of the human burial, along with the animal, and nine intact pots and one degenerated bronze pot were collected by the department during the exploration. The funerary material along with the skeleton has been identified as a pendent and mask. These are made of gold. These findings show that the person belongs to a rich family and, at the same time, they have faith in the rituals. The primary anthropological analysis shows that the skeleton was about 10-15 years old at the time of death.

The existence of cup marks, dots, and pits found in mid-central Himalayan archaeologists has given archaeologists interest in confirming archaeological material related to megalithic burials (Joshi, 1986; Naithani, 1995). Earlier workers have reported the existence of burials of Kumaon in Devidhura in Pithoragarh (Henwood, 1856), Dwarhat in Almora (Carnac, 1877) and Garhwal Himalaya (Dabral, 1968). However, the excavation by the department of history and archaeology (Garhwal University) in the area

of Ramganga Valley in the Kumaon Himalaya from Ganai to Bikyasen has given the focus of archaeologists to the Megalithic tradition. The megalithic burials discovered in the Sanana and Baseri, situated in the Ramganga valley, foothills of the Kumaun Himalaya, have yielded a human skeleton, which was identified as a skull, femur, tibia-fibula, upper jaw (maxilla) and lower jaw (mandible). The morphological analysis shows that the skull - I belongs to a man who was more than 60 years old at the time of death, however the skull – II belongs to him. He is less than 40 years old as the cranial suture is not fused.

The characteristic feature of Baseri was a group of urn burials, but these urn burials are protected by a stone wall. The burial urn had been found in a large handmade jar, measuring 48cm to 56cm in diameter. The mat impression and ripple marks have been found on the outer surface of the jar.

The Ranihat, an early historic site, is situated on the right bank of Alaknanda in Tehri Garhwal (Nautiyal & Khanduri, 1977). The cultural deposit thickness is 3.25m. However, the Ranihat dates from the 6th century B. C. to 12th century A. D. The excavation yielded pottery red ware and comprised terracotta objects, human and animal figurines, and copper and iron objects.

The animal remains from Ranihat are found in the limb bones and limb girdles of buffaloes, goats, and cattle. Another part of the animal's remains has been identified as ribs, teeth, the sternum, and parts of the thoracic region. An early historic site of Supana in district Tehri on the left bank of the Alaknanda River. The excavations of this site were conducted by the Department of History and Archaeology (Garhwal University) during the year 1998. The excavation exposed two stone walls that cut each other diagonally at a depth of 1.25 mt. However, a large number of plain Red ware with various types of design, pottery, a large number of iron tools (about 50 in number) and iron slag, of different shapes and sizes, some copper objects have been found from excavations.

A large number of animal bone remains have been found in the Supana. The faunal remains in the form of limbs, teeth, ribs, skulls, jaws, and vertebrae of domesticated animals like cattle, pigs, and goats have been found at the site. The occurrence of a large number of charred and uncharred bones from this level proves that these domesticated animals were butchered to fulfill their food requirements. However, the remains of fish vertebrae are one of the important findings, which shows that the inhabitants of Supana have also taken fish for their dietary purposes.

The department of history and archaeology (Garhwal University) also excavated an early historical site of Ufalda near Srinagar in the Alaknanda Valley. The site is located on a small hillock in the Alaknanda valley, about 4 Km south of Srinagar. The excavation yielded a large number of plain red wares and other antiquities belonging to the early medieval period. The shapes of pottery include vases, storage jars,

bowls, lamps, lids, miniature bowls etc. The number of antiquities is meager and poor, as only two arrow heads, a few bangles and terracotta, and a hopscotch are found. The animal remains included limbs, ribs, teeth, femurs, jaws, and vertebrae of domestic animals such as cattle, pigs and sheep. Besides these, a large number of charred and uncharred bones from the excavation have been found, suggesting that these domesticated animals might have been butchered for their dietary requirements.

Table 1. *Showing different archeological sites of Garhwal Himalaya*

Site	Cultural context	Chronology	Archaeology	Artifacts
Malari (Human & Horse)	Megalithic culture	1000 B. C.	Cave burial	Gold Mask and Pendent, Pottery, iron tools, Bronze bowl.
Malari (Human)	Medieval Period	1600A. D.	Intact condition	No artefacts.
Ufalda	Early historical	7 th –8 th cent. A. D.	Settlement	Arrowheads, few bangles and terracotta hopscotch.
Supana	Late- Gupta period	4 th cent. A. D.	-do-	Iron objects, copper bangle, antimony road, bead etc.
Thapli	Painted Grey Ware culture(PGW)	140B. C. (PRL-date)	-do-	Pottery, Terracotta bird, terracotta ghata - shaped bead, copper bangle, nail purer, etc.

2. Bone Chemistry and Palaeodiet

Subsistence is one of the basic requirements for all needs. The preparation of food by the exploitation of resources (plants, cereals, grain, tubers, and animals) shed light on the consumption of food by ancient populations. The carbonized grains, burned and charred bone, and cut marks on the bones found from the excavation give indirect evidence of the food practices of ancient communities. The material found in the excavation gives some clues about the subsistence pattern adopted by the communities. However, the material related to the materials gives evidence of the climate as well as the flora of the site. The cut marks on the bones of archaeofaunal remains give evidence of butchering practice. However, these signals cannot give the absolute value of dietary intake. The porous bone (e. g. fish bone) and vegetable

remains were not preserved for a long time at an archaeological site, so the exploitation of these belongings by the communities for their dietary purposes could not be done in a simple way. The scientific methods based on isotopes and trace elemental analysis give an exact picture of the subsistence pattern exploited by the ancient population.

Researchers of the interdisciplinary field of archaeology, anthropology and history are engaged in the field of palaeodietary studies. However, the evolutionary food class for humans, grains and legumes, carries with them certain health risks that rise with elevated levels of consumption. However, these factors have seldom been considered in any depth by conventional nutritional research due to a lack of appreciation of the potential ramifications tied to the very late role of these foods in human dietary evolution. Focusing primarily on grains, this exploration looks at the reasons behind the problematic nature of grains and legumes from both an evolutionary standpoint and recent research that has uncovered evidence of their mismatch with human physiology at the genetic level. The discipline is further improving its validity through scientific appreciation. The modern scientific techniques developed in this area are trace elemental analysis and isotopic analysis. A comprehensive overview of the diet of populations can tell us about the vegetarian diet as well as about the meaty diet of our early ancestors. The scientific evidence has also told us about the palaeodietary signal found in the bones of the ancient population recovered from the excavation. A complete study of the stable isotopes and trace elemental signals in the bone gives the exact meaning of the diet. Scientific evidence from evolution and anthropological research about the diet and health of early humans, recent primitive peoples, and animals is becoming more rigorous and well-defined. Now this knowledge has begun to gel via the new field of research known as palaeodiet.

The human skeleton is basically a structural framework for supporting our bodies. The anthropometric analysis of bones provides valuable information about the status of health, nutrition, growth, and disease individuals. The nature and type of diet taken by individuals influences the growth and development of the bones, and in earlier studies, it was found that the chemical and biochemical signatures of the bones are influenced to a great extent by dietary intake (Price, 1989; Price et. al, 1985). Such dietary signatures are reflected in the trace elements and isotopic ratios of the bones (Price, 1989). These signals remain in the bone even after the death of an individual and can be retrieved for use in the reconstruction of past human diets. This observation has been validated by experimental studies on laboratory animals (Lambert et. al, 1993) and modern populations of human beings (O'Connell & Hedges, 1999). Therefore, it forms the basis of palaeodietary studies.

Conclusion

In recent years, studies on prehistoric subsistence and food practices have attained worldwide attention as the focus of the archaeologist has also shifted from the conventional issues and problems. In India, various archaeologists, in collaboration with anthropologists, have been using the tools of skeletal biology, dental palaeopathology, and anthropometry to shed light on the nutritional status and status of health of individuals in prehistoric and proto-historic communities belonging to different cultural phases of Indian archaeology. In recent years, advances in bone chemistry have allowed archaeologists to exploit the analytical tools of isotopes and trace elements to investigate the diet of prehistoric human populations, which otherwise would not be discernible through conventional methods. From a wider perspective, palaeodietary studies have become a new paradigm in multidisciplinary archaeological or anthropological research. Garhwal Himalaya is about to become virgin in the field of palaeodietary research. However, the present study has been done through palaeodietary research on the basis of isotopic analysis and trace element analysis. The studies have shown that the horses domesticated by the Megalithic inhabitants around 100B. C. at Malari (12,000feet) in the high altitude Himalaya were primarily grazed on C3 grasses ($\delta^{13}\text{C} -19.39\text{‰}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N} +8\text{‰}$), which had high nitrogen rich contents. The modern samples of cattle ($\delta^{13}\text{C} -18.27\text{‰}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N} +8.21\text{‰}$) also indicate the similar practice of grazing on C3 grasses as found in the horses of Megalithic people. The carbon and nitrogen isotope signatures on the skeletal remains of an individual ($\delta^{13}\text{C} -12\text{‰}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N} +10.15\text{‰}$) datable to 1600 A. D. at Malari also provides a picture of his palaeodiet and gives a strong indication that man subsisted on a diet that was mainly based on C4 crops (possibly amaranthus and millets), but at the same time also heavily consumed a high protein diet, which came only from the consumption of meat. The practice of a diet based on high consumption of meat is still prevalent at high altitudes where the villagers do not have sufficient stocks of crops throughout the year. Therefore, inhabitants largely subsist on meat for their dietary requirements.

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